

CONFLICTS BETWEEN STUDENTS AT SCHOOL

D. Usmonova,

QVPMM Pedagogika, psixologiya va ta'lim
menijmenti kafedراسي dotsent

Annotation

Tolerance is not concession, discrimination or pretension, but above all, an active attitude formed on the basis of recognition of universal human rights and fundamental freedoms. This article talks about the formation and development of tolerant attitude among students.

Key words: xenophobia, society, conflictology, psychology, antic, method.

Schools are characterized by different types of conflicts. Pedagogical field is a combination of all types of purposeful formation of a person, the essence of which is the activity of transferring and mastering social experience. Therefore, there is a need for favorable social and psychological conditions that provide mental comfort for the teacher, student and parents. In the field of public education, it is customary to distinguish four subjects of activity: student, teacher, parents and administrator. Depending on the interaction of the subjects, the following types of conflicts can be distinguished: student - student; student - teacher; student - parents; student - administrator; teacher - teacher; teacher - parents; teacher - administrator; parents - parents; parents - administrator; administrator - administrator. The most common leadership conflicts among students reflect the struggle between two or three leaders and their groups for supremacy in the classroom. In high school, a group of boys and a group of girls often fight. A conflict may arise between three or four teenagers and the whole class, or a conflict may arise between one student and the class.

The teacher's personality has a great influence on the conflicting behavior of schoolchildren. Its influence can manifest itself in different aspects. First, the way a teacher interacts with other students serves as a model for reproduction in relationships with peers. Research shows that the first teacher's communication style and pedagogical tactics have a significant impact on the formation of interpersonal relationships between students and classmates and parents. The personal style of communication and the pedagogical tactics of "cooperation" determine the most conflicting relationships between children and each other. However, only a small number of elementary teachers master this method. Elementary school teachers with a functional style of communication follow one of the tactics ("dictation" or "guardianship") that increase the tension of interpersonal relations in the classroom. A large number of conflicts characterize the relationships in the classrooms of "authoritarian" teachers and in the middle school age. This does not necessarily mean suppressing them. Depending on the situation, administrative intervention may be necessary or just good advice. The involvement of those who are in conflict in joint activities, the participation of other students, especially the class leaders, in resolving the conflict, etc., have a positive effect. not possible. Today, the conflict with children whose living conditions cannot be called comfortable is a common part of reality. According to M.M. According to Rybakova, among the conflicts between the teacher and the student, the following conflicts stand out:

- activities resulting from the student's educational activities and extracurricular activities;
- behavior (action) resulting from student's violation of the rules of behavior in and outside the school;
- relationships that arise in the field of emotional and personal relationships between students and teachers.

Activity conflicts arise between the teacher and the student and are manifested by the student's refusal to complete the educational task or poorly performing it. Similar conflicts often occur with students who have learning difficulties; when the teacher teaches the subject for a short time in the class and the relationship between him and the student is limited only to academic work. Recently, such conflicts have been increasing as a result of the teacher's excessive demands for the mastery of the subject, as a means of punishing those who break the discipline. Such situations often cause talented, independent students to drop out of school, and for others, their overall motivation to learn decreases. creates new problems and conflicts, in which other students participate; It is easier to prevent conflicts in educational activities than to successfully solve them. It is very important for the teacher to be able to correctly determine his position in the conflict, because if the class team is on his side, he has an acceptable way out of the current situation. lin will be easier to find. If the class begins to have fun with the disciplinarian or takes an ambiguous position, this will lead to negative consequences (for example, conflicts may become permanent).

Conflicts in relationships often arise as a result of the teacher's easy handling of problematic situations and, as a rule, last for a long time. These conflicts take on a personal meaning and cause long-term enmity between the student and the teacher, which destroys their relationship for a long time.

Literature

1. Kjell L. A. Personality theories: basic principles, research and application: a textbook for universities / L. A. Kjell, D. Ziegler. St. Petersburg: Peter, 1997. 606 p.
2. Shabolina V.V. Psychology of addictive behavior: a pattern of behavior associated with the use of drugs and other psychoactive substances –/ V.V. Saint-Petersburg: Saint-Petersburg publishing house. Univ., 2004. 336 p.

3. Shakurov R. Kh. The causes of conflicts in pedagogical teams –and methods of their elimination / R. Kh., B. S. Alisherov // Psychological issues. 1986. No. 6. B. 67-76.

